

Kinetics of the Decomposition of Ce(IV) Chloride Complex in Nitric Acid Medium and the Absorption Spectra of the Complex

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The decomposition kinetics of the Ce(IV) chloride complex in nitric acid medium has been studied. The decomposition rate is found to be of first order with respect to the coloured complex. The apparent activation energy and entropy of activation are found to be 14.8 kcal./mole and -12.3 (e.u.) respectively. The absorption spectra of the complex have also been studied.

From the study of the kinetics of decomposition of the chloro complex of Ce(IV) in sulphuric and perchloric acid media, the present authors found the decomposition reaction to be of first order¹. In the present communication the authors have studied the kinetics of the decomposition reaction of the chloro complex, formed by the interaction of Ce(IV) nitrate and HCl in nitric acid medium where the concentration of the latter is high. The absorption spectra of the complex have also been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials were of the highest purity available. Both HCl and Ce(IV) nitrate were of AnalaR variety. The solution of ceric ammonium nitrate was made in HNO₃ medium.

Decomposition of the complex was followed in a Klett Summerson photoelectric colorimeter using green filters¹. The optical density was determined in the similar manner as in our previous communications¹.

Order of Reaction.—Decomposition rate of the complex was determined at three HCl concentrations, viz., 6*N*, 5*N*, and 4*N*. The concentration of Ce(IV) nitrate used was exactly *M*/20. The order of the reaction was found to be the same as mentioned in our previous communications¹. From the slopes of the log $\{(O.D.)_t - (O.D.)_0\}$ vs. t , the velocity constants were calculated.

Effect of HNO₃.—Decomposition of the complex was retarded by HNO₃. In all the cases, concentration of the components was kept fixed and acidity was varied by addition of HNO₃. On plotting log *K* against log [H⁺] in HNO₃, a straight line was obtained (Fig 3).

Effect of HCl Concentration.—The rate constants were determined at different concentrations of HCl and a fixed concentration of HNO₃. The concentration of Ce(IV) nitrate

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solution used was $M/20$; concentrations of HCl used were $3N$, $4N$, and $6N$. With the increase in the concentration of HCl the complex decomposed with greater speed (Fig. 2).

Time in min.

FIG. 1

Time in min.

FIG. 2

Effect of Temperature.—The velocity constants were calculated at four different temperatures, viz., -5° , 4° , 10° , and 17° (Fig. 1). All these experiments were performed at identical H^+ -ion concentration and $\log K$ was then plotted against $1/T$ (Fig. 4). The apparent activation energy was calculated from the linear plot as 14.9 kcal./mole from which the average entropy of activation was found to be 12.3 (e.u.).

Log $[H^+]$

FIG. 3

 $1/T \times 10^3$.

FIG. 4

Absorption Spectra.—In all the spectral experiments the complex was stabilised by addition of $6N-H_2SO_4$ and a temperature of -4° was used; under these conditions the system remained stable for a considerable period (about 30 to 40 min.). Ceric ammonium sulphate ($M/20$ exact) and HCl ($12N$) were used. By adjusting cerio sulphate, H_2SO_4 , and

HCl, the total volume of each mixture was kept constant; in different mixtures only the concentration of Ce(IV) was varied (Fig. 5). The variation of optical density with wave length is shown in Fig. 5.

In this connection the dependence of optical density of the Ce(IV) sulphate with the addition of HCl was supported by two types of experiments in which the optical densities were followed, viz., with (i) 0.5N to 6N-HCl and 0.0125M-Ce(SO₄)₂, and (ii) 6NHCl + 0.0071M, 0.00531M, 0.00355M, 0.00177M, 0.00105M, and 0.00035M ceric sulphate. These are illustrated in Fig. 6 (curves 1 and 2 respectively).

DISCUSSION

Similar to the cases of the decomposition of the chloro complex in sulphuric acid and perchloric acid media⁴, the reaction in this case (nitric acid medium) is also of the first order. Moreover, the amount of complex formation is proportional to the HCl concentration and at a constant temperature the rate is independent of the acid concentration. Addition of more nitric acid (*i.e.*, NO₃⁻ ions) here also diminishes the reaction rate.

With a view to comparing the apparent activation energy (14.8 kcal./mole) in the HNO₃ medium, one would find that this value falls intermediate between the energies in the case of H₂SO₄ medium (19.3 kcal./mole) and HClO₄ medium (6.3 kcal./mole). These values suggest that the decomposition rate of the complex in the acid media concerned is in the order: HClO₄ > HNO₃ > H₂SO₄.

The effect of anions to reduce the rate of decomposition can presumably be explained in the following way. Ce(IV) salt reacts with HCl in an acid medium (say H₂SO₄) to form Ce(IV) chloride complex which decomposes. This complex keeps in its vicinity some SO₄²⁻

ions because of the complex-forming affinity of $Ce(IV)$ ion with SO_4^{2-} . The accumulation of adjacent SO_4^{2-} ion retards the decomposition of the complex; the more concentrated is this anion, the more stable is the complex or, in other words, less is the decomposition rate. In other acid media (HNO_3 and $HClO_4$) the respective anions accumulate and try to reduce the decomposition rate. But since the tendency of complex formation of these anions with $Ce(IV)$ is in the order: $ClO_4^- < NO_3^- < SO_4^{2-}$, the activation energy also follows the same order.

FIG. 6

The absorption peaks in Fig. 5 are solely due to ceric chloride complex as ceric sulphate absorbed maximum in the UV region. It is evident that only for $Ce(IV)$ concentrations of $0.0125M$ and $0.010M$, the absorption maximum corresponds to $450 m\mu$, whereas for $0.0075M$, $0.0025M$, $0.00125M$, and $0.000625M$, the respective peaks are at $440 m\mu$, $420 m\mu$, $400 m\mu$, and $380 m\mu$. Except the second case, the maximum has been found to occur 20 units less when the concentration of $Ce(IV)$ is being reduced to half. It can be inferred from this observation that the existence of ceric chloride complex is not one under the experimental conditions, but a good number of unstable complexes exists in solution, depending on the $Ce(IV)$ and HCl ratios in the mixtures. Within our experimental performance we have only obtained evidence for five of such complexes. So the kinetics of the decomposition is actually the decomposition of a number of chloride complexes and the rate constants and the thermodynamic data that have been calculated are the overall values. The variation of optical density with the variation in the concentration of HCl and of $Ce(IV)$ are shown in Fig. 6. In no case a linear variation is obtained.

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